

Psychological Perspectives On Sin and Guilt

Jose Parappully, SDB

Founder-Director, Bosco Psychological Services,
New Delhi

Abstract: Though Psychology in general has neglected the exploration of sin per se, some attempt has been made to address the nature of evil, particularly in the Jungian tradition. The views of some contemporary psychologists, especially on the origins of evil, and reasons for its perpetuation are outlined. Guilt is presented as a self-conscious emotion, linked to but distinct from shame. The psychoanalytic understanding of guilt as an unconscious force at work in most neurosis is highlighted. Guilt is also addressed as a component of grief and mourning as well as a major contributor to depression. The consequences of excessive feelings of guilt and of its absence are presented.

Key words: Psychology. Sin. Evil. Guilt. Scrupulosity. Moral Disengagement

Exploration of the psychological perspectives on sin and guilt is a challenge. There are very few references to the two concepts in psychological theory and research. Index pages of books on psychology make almost no mention of sin. Only a few of these books carry reference to guilt, and these few references are mostly in relation to psychoanalysis, depression or mourning.

One major reason for this lacuna is that the discipline of psychology considers sin to be a religious construct. For years psychology had very deliberately chosen to distance itself from religion, if not take an adversarial stance toward it (Post, 1992). It is only very recently that the psychological and psychiatric establishments have begun to take an active interest in religion and spirituality. In fact today there is a good deal of research done in regard to the health benefits of the

practice of religion and spirituality (Koenig, 1998; Pargament, 1997; Silberman, 2005). Yet, sin remains a concept that psychologists want little to do with. One reason for this is psychology's effort to be recognised and accepted as a science. Science is considered to be a value-free activity. Study of sin requires a priori value assumptions about what is good and evil, and that is not permissible under traditional science (Peck, 1988a).

What is most surprising is that even publications on the psychology of religion do not explore sin or guilt. The great classic in psychology of religion, William James's *Varieties of Religious Experience* (1902/1978) has only a few passing references to sin. Some of the more recent and well-received publications on the psychology of religion (Hood, Spilka, Hunsberger & Gorsuch, 1996; Paloutzian & Park, 2005), or those on the role of religion in mental health (Koenig, 1998; Shafranske, 1996) do not carry chapters on sin or guilt. Even their index pages make very few references to sin or guilt.

Shafranske (1996), though a large book (617 pages) devotes less than half a page, just two paragraphs, to "Sin and Suffering." The term guilt does not appear in its index. In Hood, Spilka, Hunsberger and Gorsuch (1996), sin receives brief mention on five pages. One reference is in regard to the functionality of sin within fundamentalism and sin's role in religious conversion. Another is to religion's concern with sin and the impact of this concern on mental health. The third reference is to the fear of sin contributing to scrupulosity. Guilt is mentioned in the book on five pages in very similar contexts, mostly in conjunction with sin. Koenig (1998) has four brief references to sin in Catholic and Jewish traditions.

Sin and guilt receive a little more attention in Paloutzian and Park (2005), but not much more. They discuss the role of indulgence in sin and restraining from it in the regulation of negative affect. They show how preoccupation with sin can result in what they describe as the pathology of ritual. "Normal uses of ritual can shade into obsession, compulsivity, and a dogmatic rigidity that takes over one's daily life" (p. 369). An extreme example of such pathology is the disorder of scrupulosity in which one suffers from recurrent and severe doubts as to whether one has sinned. The individual develops obsessive rituals

both to counter such thoughts or as atonement for sins thought to have been committed.

Paloutzian and Park (2005) also address the relationship between sin and virtuous striving. They discuss how individuals can respond in healthy ways to the reality of their sinfulness. Punitive feelings toward the self consequent to sin can lead to low self-esteem, anxiety and depression. Willingness to acknowledge one's sins and open oneself to God's love and forgiveness can facilitate self-forgiveness and forgiveness of others, both of which have beneficial effect on well-being.

O. Hobart Mowrer, himself a distinguished psychologist, challenged the reluctance and the aversion of the psychological community to address the reality of sin. In an article published in the American Psychological Association's flagship journal, the *American Psychologist*, Mowrer (1960) suggested that it would be more appropriate and helpful for psychologists and psychotherapists to consider the states of mind and being that lead to neurosis "sin" rather than "sickness."

Mowrer began the article (1960) citing his experience after presenting a paper at the 1959 APA Convention on "Constructive Aspects of the Concept of Sin in Psychotherapy." Psychologists and psychiatrists asked him: "But *why* must you use that awful word 'sin,' instead of some more neutral term such as 'wrongdoing,' 'irresponsibility,' or 'immorality'?" He described how toward the end of a summer term of teaching at a prestigious University, a student in his class on Personality Theory said to him: "Did you know that near the beginning of this course you created a kind of scandal on this campus?" The student explained that Mowrer had once used the word "sin" without saying "so called" or making a joke about it. The student went on to say that such a reference to sin "was virtually unheard-of in a psychology professor and had occasioned considerable dismay and perplexity" (p. 301).

Mowrer (1960) suggested that it would serve psychology better to consider a "neurotic" as one who is "sinful" rather than as one who is "sick." He particularly castigated the Freudian hypothesis that the "neurotic" person is not responsible for his/her suffering, that it is

only the result of a too severe superego. He considered the term “sin” the lesser of two evils than “sickness.” He also suggested a “closer and friendlier relationship ... with religion and theology.” (p. 303).

The comments from other reputed psychologists published in the *American Psychologist* following Mowrer’s (1960) article were mostly unfavourable, indicating his suggestions were not very welcome in the psychological community. Albert Ellis (1960) found fault with the syllogism Mowrer used and observed that using the religiously neutral concepts of “wrongdoing” and “irresponsibility” that Mowrer had abandoned in favour of “sin” would actually be more effective in helping the “neurotic” address his/her difficulties.

Goodhue Livingston (1960) expressed strong opposition to Mowrer’s argument for introducing the concept of sin into psychotherapy. He observed that clinicians are not concerned with “guilt” as a theological problem, but “the poisonous, corrosive guilt which destroys the patient’s soul, leads him to suicide, murder, self-destruction... No better term exists for this phenomenon than sickness—sickness of the mind, perhaps, but sickness nonetheless” (p. 714).

Hans Strupp’s (1960) comment focused more on Mowrer’s “persistent and egregious misinterpretation of Freud’s conception of neurosis” (p. 714) than on Mowrer’s observations on sin. Strupp concluded his comment stating that the “hope for psychology as a science... does not lie in an alliance with religion or theology; it lies in a willingness to look at facts without moralizing about them...” (p. 715).

George H. Frank (1960) also took objection to what he saw as Mowrer’s misrepresentation of psychoanalysis and his dismissive attitude toward it. He defended the validity and usefulness of understanding neurosis as sickness rather than sin: “the ‘original sin’ of the neurotic would seem to be to have been born with a nervous and/or metabolic system that predisposes the individual to undue anxiety under stress” (p. 716).

Daniel N. Wiener, another reputed psychologist, expressed a different view (1961). He critiqued the four previous comments and saw some validity in Mowrer’s suggestions. He admitted that Mowrer

caused a "a ruckus by using the word 'sin' because of its religious connotations....," but went on to add that by using it, Mowrer had "brought into far clearer focus than anyone else in our profession currently our need as therapists and patients for a guiding sense of values and humanity" (p. 260).

Mowrer is not the only one who saw the impoverishment of the field of psychology by its aversion to the use of the term 'sin.' In his classic work, *Whatever Became of Sin?* (1973) the eminent psychoanalyst Karl Menninger lamented the disappearance of sin—"a word once in everyone's mind, but now rarely if ever heard" (p. 13)—from social as well as intellectual discourse. He defined sin as "behaviour that violates the moral code or the individual conscience or both; behaviour which pains or harms or destroys my neighbour—or me, myself." (p. 17). He believed "there is 'sin' which is expressed in ways which cannot be subsumed under the verbal artefacts such as 'crime,' 'disease,' 'delinquency,' or 'deviancy.' There is immorality; there is unethical behaviour; there is wrongdoing." And he demonstrated "that there is usefulness in retaining the concept, and indeed the word SIN..." (p. 46). Making theologian Paul Tillich's words his own, Menninger declared "There are no substitutes for words like 'sin' and 'grace'." (p. 47)

Menninger (1973) bemoaned the tendency of psychologists to explain away what was considered sin as disorder. He believed that mental health and moral health were identical and that the recognition of the pervasive reality of sin and guilt would offer suffering humanity real hope and comfort. He gave a clarion call to consider moral values an essential aspect of psychiatric and psychological enterprise, for there are some individuals, he declared, "whose sins are greater than their symptoms." (p. 49). His call, however, did not evoke any appreciable positive response. The psychological and psychiatric community continued to resist incorporation of religious and spiritual values, and particularly the notion of sin, into psychotherapy.

Sin as Evil

While sin is not a concept popular with psychologists they have shown some interest in the exploration of evil. Carl Jung especially has devoted much attention to evil. Evil, especially in its manifestation

as shadow, is recurrent theme in his writings. The final chapter of his autobiography *Memories, Dreams, Reflections* (1963) entitled *Late Thoughts* is mostly about evil. His *Answer to Job* (1973), “the most controversial book he has ever written” (Adler, 1973, p. v) is an attempt on Jung’s part to formulate his answers to the questions of evil and its relationship to God. Jung presented evil as the dark side – the shadow — of God.

Rejecting the doctrine of evil as the *privatio boni* (absence of good), Jung (1973) asserted that evil is a determinant of reality and something that cannot be dismissed from the world. Evil is not just the accidental lack of perfection, but an entity in itself with its own reality. However he did not see evil and good as opposite entities, but aspects of the whole. It is the nature of the self to unite good and evil. He posits such a unity to the being of the Godhead itself. For Jung, the doctrine of *privatio boni* dilutes the power and reality of evil and evokes a distorted, one-sided image of wholeness as being wholly light. Denial of the reality of evil has had nefarious consequences.

Jung not only asserted the reality of evil; he also saw evil as capable of producing good. He believed that evil had a mysterious role to play in delivering people from darkness and suffering (Jung, 1963). At the same time he also knew that evil had its characteristic psychological consequences: “the wrong we have done, thought, or intended will wreak its vengeance on our souls” (p. 329). The issue of evil is something he struggled to understand and come to terms with throughout his life.

One contemporary psychologist who has devoted a good deal of attention to the exploration of evil is M. Scot Peck. His *People of the Lie* (1983) is an exploration of evil committed by individuals. In *The Road less Travelled* (1978) too he explored sin and evil and also grace under the non-spiritual label “serendipity” (Peck, 1988b). A major chapter in that book is entitled *Toward a Psychology of Evil*. That was his effort, he said, toward the creation of a body of scientific knowledge about the subject of human evil, since there wasn’t at that time any such body of knowledge that could be considered “worthy of being dignified by the name of psychology” (1988a, p. 205).

Peck (1988a) suggested that there might be a genetic base to human evil. If this is found to be true, it opens up new avenues to explore

Original Sin not only as a theological concept but a biological and psychological reality. In fact, new research in neuroscience (Newberg & D'Aquili, 1998; Gazzaniga, 2000; Siever & Frucht, 1997) is suggesting that so much of our behaviour and experience have their sources in our genes. Hence it is not too far fetched to conclude that both good and evil inherent in human behaviour may also be dependent on our genes, on our biology. This has profound implications for our understanding of free will, of grace, of sin and guilt.

Roy Baumeister is another contemporary psychologist who explores the nature of evil. His book on *Evil* (1997) is a fascinating study of evil inherent in human violence and cruelty. He explodes the myth that evil is perpetrated by inhuman psychopaths, and demonstrates how ordinary men and women, driven by circumstances, are capable of perpetrating terrible evil. He too suggests some genetic element in the human inclination toward evil, while not discounting the contribution of culture.

Baumeister defined evil as “actions that intentionally harm other people” (1997, p. 8), and provided some answers as to why humans are led to commit evil. His definition excludes accidental or unintended harm, even though it may appear as evil to the victim. Though his focus is on aggression and violence, his exploration provides insights that help us understand evil in general.

Baumeister presented victimisation as the essence of evil and categorised the question of evil as “a victim’s question” (p. 1). Evil is in the eye of the beholder. This is not a denial of the objective reality of evil, but that often the individual who perpetrates it does not recognise it as evil, rather finds all kinds of seemingly justifiable reasons for the deed, even presenting it as beneficial for the victim or society. Most perpetrators of evil consider themselves as good people trying to defend themselves or their group against the forces of evil. They see no evil in what they do.

Often perpetrators consider their evil action as something ordinary and unremarkable. Even though, the first time an evil action, say killing someone, is committed, it might be upsetting or even traumatic, somehow perpetrators get used to the killing, and take the killing in their stride as though it was something ordinary.

Baumeister presented egotism—the desire to consider oneself important, more powerful than others—as another pervasive cause of evil. Perpetrators of evil are often people who think very highly of themselves, and want to be recognised for the power they wield. Greed, lust and ambition—in other words, the dynamics of self-promotion—drive people to evil.

Baumeister presented failures in self-control as the immediate or proximate cause of evil: “regardless of the root causes of violence, the immediate cause is often a breakdown of self-control” (1997, p. 14). What is needed for people to commit evil is having the reasons to restrain themselves taken away, rather than having reasons to commit the evil.

The Psychological Cost of Evil

Janoff Bulman’s (1992) understanding of the dynamics of trauma has implications also for the psychological understanding of evil and its consequences. Evil, like trauma, shatters some basic assumptions about the self and the world.

Janoff-Bulman (1992) described the experience of trauma as the shattering of three basic assumptions which people make to construct a coherent cognitive framework to maintain a sense of well-being and significance. These are: (a) the world is benevolent; (b) the world is meaningful; and (c) the self is worthy. People in general believe that they live in a benevolent and safe world rather than a malevolent and hostile one. A meaningful world is one in which they perceive a relationship between action and outcome. Such a perception enables them to believe that misfortune is not haphazard and arbitrary, and that they can control what happens to them. The assumption of self-worth involves a global evaluation of the self in which people perceive themselves as good, capable and moral individuals.

These basic assumptions provide individuals with a sense of invulnerability, a sense of confidence and trust, a general optimism that things will work out well, that they are safe and protected. Even though there is “a powerful tendency to maintain rather than change the fundamental beliefs that have enabled us to make sense of ourselves and our world,” Janoff-Bulman observed, some events are so powerful

that they destroy these assumptions (1992, p. 40). Any event that shatters these assumptions leads to an intense psychological crisis through “the disintegration of one’s inner world” (p. 63).

Evil, particularly of the heinous kind, can be described as a traumatic experience for the victim; and like trauma, evil shatters the victim’s basic assumptions about life, self and others and disintegrates the inner world, leading to a variety of painful psychological consequences, including severe mental illness.

Evil and Moral Disengagement

Pioneering social psychologist Albert Bandura provides some explanations as to why evil continues unabated. He places the blame on the moral disengagement in the perception of evil. In his recent invited address at the American Psychological Association’s Annual Convention in San Francisco (2007) he described the dynamics of moral disengagement. Baumeister (1997) also presented similar dynamics.

Moral disengagement was Bandura’s (2007) explanation for large scale inhumanity perpetrated by people who are benevolent and even compassionate in other areas of their lives – good people doing bad things. He outlined four mechanisms of moral disengagement: moral justification; minimising consequences; non-responsibility; and de-humanisation .

Moral Justification: Perpetrators numb themselves morally by finding justifications for their evil deeds. Mass killings, for example, are often carried out under religious motives. We are familiar with holy wars of today where killing is legitimised by recourse to sacred scriptures and religious injunctions. This however is not a new phenomenon. The Crusades were a killing spree sanctified by the religious imperative.

Minimising: Sanitisation of language or euphemistic labelling is an effective means to minimise the perception of evil. Sanitisation helps to minimise the the enormity and crassness of evil. Perpetrators of evil can play games with words, making the horrible appear as mundane and innocent. In war, brutality can be disguised by using such innocent sounding euphemisms as “coercive diplomacy” for carpet

bombing; and “collateral damage” for killing of innocent civilians. Genocide can be sanitised by using such euphemisms as “final solution” as in Nazi Germany or “bush clearing” as in Rwanda, and mass killings for political gain as “ethnic cleansing,” as in Bosnia. A classic, and somewhat laughable, attempt at euphemistic labelling is that of a US Senator who proudly declared: “Capital punishment is our society’s recognition of the sanctity of human life” (Bandura, 2007).

Non-Responsibility: Perpetrators can engage in dubious cognitive distortions to reduce or deny personal responsibility. They can, for example, present themselves as dutiful functionaries, honouring their obligations by blindly carrying out orders such as the Nazis did and feel no personal responsibilities for the harm they cause. Those who issued orders can absolve themselves attributing responsibility to groupthink.

Division of labour and the distance between initial and end process can make individual tasks performed in detached isolation look harmless, even though the end result of the combined actions by different people is horrendous. Bandura (2007) cited mass production and sale of weapons of destruction as an example. The entire arms industry, “a death industry,” is divided into several independent sections. People engaged in one section has no links with others. For example, there are several intermediaries between the design of weapon and their end use in killing innocent people, such as people involved in manufacture, marketing, shipping and so on. Those engaged in design, for example, are far removed from those who actually use the weapons they have designed and can feel no responsibility in the killing. Fractioning the enterprise, those involved see themselves as guiltless, while promoting a death industry. The arms seller, for example, can claim he or she is just doing a business; the designer can claim he or she is being creative and promoting science. Both can eschew responsibility for the killing they have facilitated.

The death in the gas chambers of Nazi concentration camps was the end result of a series of decisions and actions by different people. The woman who betrayed the Jewish family to the Nazi authorities can say she just did her duty. The man who drove the death train can say he just did his duty. Both can claim they were not responsible for what happened

in the gas chambers. And so on and on. Each person in the chain of events can disown responsibility and claim immunity.

So also in war, the one who gives the command to carpet bomb innocent civilians thousands of miles away from his or her command and control centre does not see or hear the destruction caused on the ground and can be numb to the consequences as to his or her own role. The gulf between decision makers and executioners helps to dissipate responsibility and guilt. Destruction inflicted remotely by computers (e.g., smart bombs controlled from the USA and dropped thousands of miles away in Iraq by pilot-less drones) is another example of dissipation of responsibility which enables easy perpetration of evil. (For further description of mechanisms of denial and self-absolution of war atrocities, see also Menninger, 1973, pp. 101-107).

Dehumanising: Labelling victims as subhuman is one strategy used to distance oneself from them and hence making it easier to perpetrate evil on them. Labelling the enemy as something other than human is a crafty yet subtle means of justifying evil. One avoids guilt by ejecting the victims from the human community, and thus denying any social bonds with them. Demonising one's enemy such as labelling countries and organisations or individuals as "evil empire," "axis of evil" or "Satan" makes it easier to legitimise attacking or killing them.

Labelling one's enemy as the "other" is another strategy. People feel less empathy toward those they consider as not part of the in-group. Labelling victims as other reduces social bonds and helps to eliminate guilt. It is hard to experience empathy without social bonds. Lack of empathy results in lack of guilt. And without guilt coming in the way, it is much easier to perpetrate evil.

Guilt

While sin does not get very much attention in psychological literature, guilt fares better. Since guilt is an emotion and there is much interest in emotions in psychology, guilt elicits a good deal of interest and attention. Since imbalances in emotions are major features of depression and mourning, guilt is explored mostly in relation to these two human experiences. Guilt has also been of great interest to psychoanalysts, who speak of the unconscious need for self-punishment.

According to Michael Lewis (1993), the eminent researcher in the field of emotions, guilt is a self-conscious emotion. These are emotions that emerge later in life than emotions in general and require certain cognitive abilities for their elicitation. Unlike emotions that appear early such as joy, sadness, fear and anger, these do not have clear, specific elicitors. Self-conscious emotions require classes of events that can be identified only by the individuals themselves. Their elicitation “involves elaborate cognitive processes that have, at their heart, the notion of self...” (p. 563). “Self-conscious evaluative emotions first involve a set of standards, rules or goals (SRGs). These SRGs are inventions of the culture that are transmitted to children and involve their learning of, and willingness to consider, these SRGs as their own” (p. 564). Secondly, there is self-evaluation of one’s actions in regard to these SRGs.

Guilt and Shame

Often guilt and shame are confused conceptually. Though both guilt and shame are self-conscious emotions, there are significant theoretical differences between the two. Guilt arises from behaviour and shame from one’s sense of self.

In guilt one believes one has done something wrong. It is related to behaviour and is accompanied by feelings of regret and negative self-evaluation and a desire for atonement. One berates oneself for what one has done. Guilt, thus, is related to one’s action and not to the whole self. It is a specific and focused response to a moral transgression. The sense of transgression is stronger when one feels one has wronged or harmed an innocent other. There is no need for actual transgression for one to experience guilt, a fantasised wrong is sufficient (Lazarus, 1991; Lewis, 1993).

Shame, on the other hand, has to do with how one feels about oneself. Shame involves a sense of inadequacy, a feeling one has blundered, and is accompanied by embarrassment and wish to disappear, not to be seen. One feels disgraced especially in the eyes of someone whose opinion is very important. The core relational theme, the central meaning and harm-benefit appraisal pattern, in shame is failure to live up to an ego-ideal. Shame is an insult to one’s self-image (Lazarus, 1991).

In guilt the cognitive-attribitional process focuses on the action of the self while in shame the focus is on the totality of the self. Moreover, since in guilt the focus is on the specific, individuals are able to rid themselves of this emotional state through corrective action. Consequently the intensity of the negative emotion in guilt is less than in shame and more capable of dissipation. However, if one is not able to take corrective action to repair the transgression or its consequences, the guilt experience can be converted into one of shame (Lewis, 1993).

In guilt one fears punishment; in shame one fears exposure, alienation and rejection.

Roots of Guilt

Although there are many sources of guilt, they can all be subsumed under one major dynamic, namely, violation of a personal standard. One judges oneself as having done something that leads to a sense of badness which lowers self-esteem. This sense of badness is also accompanied by a fear or expectation of punishment and a feeling that one should make retribution (Rando, 1993). Not only does one feel accountable for the transgression, but also believes that it was in one's power to have acted otherwise and that one should have. "The core relational theme for guilt is self-blame for a moral transgression, even though it may have occurred only in fantasy or imagination" (Lazarus, 1993, p. 32).

Psychoanalytic Understanding

The personal standards whose violation leads to guilt derive from the super ego—the mechanism by which the standards of the parents are incorporated into the self, specifically via the child's fear that the parents will respond to transgression, particularly to their hostile and sexual impulse gratification, by withdrawal of love or even by punishment. The stronger the superego injunctions, the greater the feelings of guilt. This is the psychoanalytic understanding of the source of guilt (Freud 1961; Lazarus, 1991; Lewis, 1993)

For Freud, guilt is "The tension between the harsh super-ego and the ego that is subjected to it" and which "expresses itself as a need for punishment" (1961). In infancy, guilt arises from fear of an authority, and particularly the fear of loss of love of that authority figure. Later,

it results from the fear of the super ego— the internalised parental injunctions in childhood and in later development the internalised societal injunctions. For this, the structure of the superego has to achieve a certain level of maturity that will evoke conflict between it and the ego. Freud equated the superego with the conscience.

Freud (1961) fixed the origin of guilt from the evolutionary perspective in the Oedipus Complex – the inherited desire to kill the father to possess the love of the mother: “We cannot get away from the assumption,” Freud asserted, “that man’s sense of guilt springs from the Oedipus Complex and was acquired at the killing of the father by the brothers banded together” (p. 78). In this view, it is the aggressive impulse, even if not acted out, directed against the father that is the source of guilt. An action carried out or merely intended can produce guilt.

Freud considered guilt to be a neurotic obsession rather than a reality-based self perception. It remains to a large extent unconscious, appearing as a sort *malaise*, an underlying dissatisfaction.

A real transgression evokes not guilt, but remorse: “When one has a sense of guilt after having committed a misdeed, and because of it, the feeling should more properly be called remorse. It relates only to a deed that has been done...” (1961, p. 79). In the case of remorse, the feeling of guilt makes itself clearly perceptible to consciousness. For Freud, guilt due to remorse, though frequent and important in its consequences, is outside the purview of psychoanalysis.

For religiously oriented persons, the superego injunctions exert a greater force, and consequently, they experience guilt more intensely: “For the more virtuous a man is, the more severe and distrustful is its [superego’s] behaviour, so that ultimately it is precisely those people who have carried saintliness furthest who reproach themselves with the worst sinfulness” (Freud, 1961, p. 73)

Erik Erikson (1950/1963; 1959/1980) expanded the Freudian psychoanalytic understanding of guilt by adding psychosocial elements to the psychosexual. Erikson counterpoised guilt against initiative at stage 3 (Locomotor-Genital) of his eight-stage developmental framework. For Erikson guilt at this stage is not just about the forbidden sexual desires and impulses that make up the Oedipal Complex. He

posited guilt in the broader context of the child's new capacities as well, such as for independent and vigorous movement; for language and imagination; for aggressive play and experimentation; and the child's new motivational drives such as struggles for autonomy over parental figures, and conflict between defiance and obedience in interpersonal relationships. Guilt arises when the child's initiatives are met with disapproval or ridicule.

Guilt in Grief and Mourning

Guilt is one of the emotional areas in which one can most commonly get trapped in the grieving process (Tatelbaum, 1980). Guilt is often the result of anger and ambivalence that a survivor feels following the death of a loved one (Rando, 1993). In complicated mourning, guilt can take destructive dimensions.

Suicidal thoughts are quite common during grieving the death of someone, especially when the death was sudden or unexpected. Often suicidal ideation and attempts result from excessive guilt and serve as self-punishment. It is very easy for the survivor to turn any thought or feeling into guilt. One can feel guilty about things done or undone, words spoken or unspoken, and even about thoughts one entertained in regard to the dead person. One can feel guilty for not feeling what one believes is to be an appropriate level of sadness. Survivors tend to recall everything negative on their part in their relationship and fail to remember their more positive contributions.

Guilt can arise if one feels some relief at the death of the loved one for some reason or other. Especially in cases where the person might have been in some way a burden, or the relationship had been a difficult or conflicted one, death sometimes can be a relief. This feeling of relief then can turn to guilt. One blames oneself for such feelings, considering them as expressions of disloyalty or lack of love.

Many kinds of unfinished business with the deceased person can appear later in the form of guilt, in the form of "if only's" and "should haves." Survivors can torment themselves endlessly with these unfinished issues. This is especially true in regard to the feeling "if only" they had done something or refrained from doing something they could have somehow prevented their loved one from dying. They burden

ourselves with unnatural responsibility for the death, convinced that their behaviour would have altered reality. (Rando, 1993; Tatelbaum, 1980; Worden, 1982).

Often people who have survived others in similar circumstances, such as the concentration camp, or atomic bombing, or even an accident, feel guilty because they survived, and others did not.

Guilt and Depression

Guilt has its painful and dysfunctional consequences. Guilt is often a major contributor to depression (*DSM_IV*, American Psychiatric Association, 1994). Preoccupations or ruminations over minor past failings are common among individuals who are depressed. They consider their condition as punishment for some wrong done in the past or something for which they feel they are to be blamed. Often their feelings of guilt are baseless, excessive and/or inappropriate. Their guilt may reach delusional proportions.

Guilt is the symptom that most discriminates between anxiety states and major depressive states (Bech, 1992). Individuals who are anxious do not experience guilt, while for depressed individuals guilt is a major source of distress and worry.

Guilt and Prosocial Behaviour

Guilt feelings can cause considerable pain and distress, and some people suffer needlessly from excessive and unreasonable guilt. However guilt also has its benefits. For example, guilt can make people behave in socially appropriate ways. As Lazarus & Lazarus (1994) pointed out,

guilt can be a very useful emotion because it helps promote socially desirable behaviour. In short, guilt is a prosocial emotion. It does this because we learn to avoid socially forbidden actions to avoid guilt feelings and social criticism or rejection. If members of society want to behave well, there is less need to police their actions compared with those who care little about social morality. People with strong guilt feelings are good to have around because they are more apt than others to be fair in their dealings. If they are extremely upright, however,

they may constrain the extent to which others could indulge themselves in disapproved pleasures. (p. 56)

In his exploration of human evil, Baumeister (1997; Baumeister, Stillwell & Heatherton, 1994) also addressed the issue of guilt. He too found a prosocial (interpersonal) benefit arising from guilt. One source of guilt is empathic consideration: the degree of guilt is often proportional to how much one cares for people. The other source, very much in keeping with the psychoanalytic understanding, is fear of losing relationships. Guilt, evoked by empathic concern and fear of losing relationships, can lead one to refrain from committing evil and to make reparation for past evil. Guilt helps to restore and strengthen the bonds between people.

Absence of Guilt

While excessive guilt causes much distress and anxiety, the inability to feel guilt too has its pathological consequences. Lack of guilt is a prominent feature of the antisocial personality disorder (*DSM-IV*, APA, 1994; Sperry, 1995). Because of the absence of guilt feelings, these individuals, usually labelled psychopaths, are much more likely than the general public to break the rules and laws of society, and to perpetrate evil. They lie, cheat and steal without any scruple. They are deceitful and manipulative. They repeatedly fail to honour their obligations. They manifest reckless disregard for the feelings, needs, rights and safety of others. They can be callous and sadistic to an extreme degree, engage in criminal activities and feel no remorse. It is not uncommon to find such antisocial and sadistic personalities even among professional religious who are normally expected to be benign and empathetic.

Sin, Guilt and Scrupulosity

Very many religiously inclined individuals suffer from scrupulosity — an excessive and inappropriate preoccupation with sin and guilt. Such preoccupation is sometimes severe enough to be labelled Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (*DSM-IV*, APA, 1994). These individuals tend to be over conscientious and excessively moralistic.

Even when they intellectually pay lip service to an unconditionally loving God, deep down scrupulous individuals experience God as

punitive, as one who would not brook even the slightest moral failure. Hence their energies are devoted to the avoidance of sin, and in case they sin, they are plagued by thoughts of punishment, and despairing of forgiveness.

This scrupulosity is more especially experienced in regard to sexuality. As psychiatrist Paul Tournier (1966) has observed, many people regard sin that has to do with sex as being in a class by itself, a sin that is outside the pale of forgiveness. They interpret as sinful many normal human experiences. As an example, a religious woman was extremely scrupulous in regard to sexuality. On one occasion when touching her breasts while showering she experienced some sexual pleasure. She felt she had committed a serious sin and was convinced that God would never forgive her and that her religious life had become a lie. That pathological feeling of guilt haunted her and influenced her subsequent life style and spirituality.

The negative images of God instilled in childhood and a sexually repressed environment which presents even slightest experience of sexual pleasure as a grave sin have been the cause of much human misery, especially among religiously oriented individuals. These individuals experience excessive guilt feelings because of their internalised images of a punitive God. Fear of sin and the consequent punishment exerts a tyrannical influence on them. They live a very controlled existence and are chronically anxious and tense.

“A real sin” observed psychiatrist Paul Tournier (1966), “can lead a person to the liberating experience of grace, whereas a fictitious sin, a suggested guilt, has no such religious result” (p. 154). Instead, it blocks the action of grace.

Conclusion

Psychology has shown some aversion to the exploration of sin. A major reason for this is psychology’s desire to separate itself from religion and theology. Another is the desire to be recognised as a scientific discipline. However, some attention has been given to the exploration of sin’s twin brother, evil, particularly in Jungian psychology. Guilt is a favourite theme in psychoanalysis. Theory and research in grief and mourning give considerable attention to guilt.

While excessive and inappropriate guilt can result in depression, a lack of guilt can lead to the formation of the antisocial personality. While a healthy sense of guilt has prosocial benefits, inappropriate guilt leads to scrupulosity, a psychological and spiritual disorder that is destructive to the life of the soul.

Notes and References

- 1 Adler, G. (1973). Editorial Note. In C. G. Jung, Answer to Job. (R. F. C. Hull Trans.) In H. Read, M. Fordham, & G. Adler (Eds.), *Bollingen Series XX. The Collected Works of C. G. Jung*. (Vol. 11, pp. v-vi). Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- 2 American Psychiatric Association. (1994). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (4th ed.). Washington, DC: Author.
- 3 Bandura, A. (2007, August 18). *Moral disengagement in the perception of inhumanities*. Invited Address. Annual Convention of the American Psychological Association. San Francisco.
- 4 Baumeister, R. F. (1997). *Evil: Inside human violence and cruelty*. New York: W. H. Freeman and Company.
- 5 Baumeister, R. F., Stillwell, A. M., & Heatherton, T. F. (1994). Guilt: An interpersonal approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, *115*(2), 243-267.
- 6 Bech, P. (1992). Symptoms and assessment of depression. In E. S. Paykel (Ed.), *Handbook of affective disorders* (2nd ed., pp. 3-24). New York: Guilford
- 7 Ellis, A. (1960). Comment: Mowrer on sin. *American Psychologist*, *15*, 713-714.
- 8 Erikson, E. (1963). *Childhood and society* (2nd Ed. Rev. & Enlarged). New York: Norton. (Original work published 1950)
- 9 Erikson, E. (1980). *Identity and the life cycle*. New York: Norton. (Original work published 1959).
- 10 Frank, G. H. (1960). Comment: Mowrer on sin. *American Psychologist*, *15*, 715-716.
- 11 Freud, S. (1961). *Civilisation and its discontents*. (J. Strachey Ed. and Trans.). New York. Norton & Norton.
- 12 Gazzaniga, M. S. (Ed.). (2000). *Cognitive neuroscience: A reader*. Malden, MA: Blackwell.
- 13 Hood, R. W., Spilka, B., Hunsberger, B., & Gorsuch, R. (1996). *The psychology of religion* (2nd ed.). New York: Guildford.

- 14 James, W. (1978). *The varieties of religious experience*. New York: Image books. (Original work published 1902)
- 15 Janoff-Bulman, R. (1992). *Shattered assumptions: Towards a new psychology of trauma*. New York: The Free Press.
- 16 Jung, C.G. (1963). *Memories, dreams reflections* (Rev. ed.). New York: Vintage Books.
- 17 Jung, C. G. (1973). *Answer to Job* (R. F. C. Hull Trans.). In H. Read, M. Fordham, & G. Adler (Eds.), *Bollingen Series XX. The Collected Works of C. G. Jung*. (Vol. 11, pp. v-vi). Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- 18 Koenig, H. G. (Ed.). (1998). *Handbook of religion and mental health*. San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- 19 Lazarus, R. S. (1991). *Emotion and adaptation*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- 20 Lazarus, R. S. (1993). Why we should think of stress as a subset of emotion. In L. Goldberger & S. Breznits (Eds.), *Handbook of stress: Theoretical and clinical aspects* (2nd ed. pp 21-39). New York: The Free Press.
- 21 Lazarus, R. S., & Lazarus, B. N. (1994). *Passion and reason: Making sense of our emotions*. New York: Oxford.
- 22 Lewis, M. (1993). Self-conscious emotions: Embarrassment, pride, shame, and guilt. In M. Lewis, & J. M. Haviland (Eds.), *Handbook of emotions* (pp. 563-573). New York: Guilford.
- 23 Livingston, G. (1960). Comment: Mowrer on sin. *American Psychologist*, 15, 714.
- 24 Menninger, K. (1973). *Whatever became of sin?* New York: Hawthorn Books.
- 25 Mowrer, O. H. (1960). "Sin," the lesser of two evils. *American Psychologist*, 15, 301-304.
- 26 Newberg, A. B., & D'Aquili, E. G. (1998). The neuropsychology of spiritual experience In H. G. Koenig (Ed.), *Handbook of religion and mental health* (pp. 75-94). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- 27 Pargament, K. I. (1997). *The psychology of religion and coping*. New York: Guilford.
- 28 Paloutzian, R. F., & Park, C. L. (2005). *Handbook of the psychology of religion and spirituality*. New York: Guilford.
- 29 Peck, M. S. (1978). *The road less travelled: A new psychology of love, traditional values and spiritual growth*. New York: Simon & Schuster.

- 30 Peck, M. S. (1983). *People of the lie: The hope for healing human evil*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- 31 Peck, M. S. (1998a). Dialogue with M. Scott Peck. In P. Woodruff & H. A. Wilmer (Ed.), *Facing evil: Light at the core of darkness* (pp. 202-207). La Salle, IL: Open Court.
- 32 Peck, M. S. (1998b). Healing institutional evil. In P. Woodruff & H. A. Wilmer (Ed.), *Facing evil: Light at the core of darkness* (pp. 99-202). La Salle, IL: Open Court.
- 33 Post, S. G. (1992). DSM-III-R and religion. *Social and Scientific Medicine*, 35 (1), 81-90.
- 34 Rando, T. A. (1993). *Treatment of complicated mourning*. Champaign, IL: Research Press.
- 35 Shafranske, E. P. (1996). *Religion and the clinical practice of psychology*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- 36 Siever, L. J. & Frucht, W. (1997). *The new view of self: How genes and neurotransmitters shape your mind, your personality, and your mental health*. New York: Macmillan.
- 37 Silberman, I. (Issue Ed.). (2005). Religion as a meaning system. *Journal of Social Issues* (I. H. Frieze, Ed.), 61 (4).
- 38 Sperry, L. (1995). *Handbook of diagnosis and treatment of the DSM-IV personality disorders*. New York: Brunner/Mazel.
- 39 Strupp, H. H. (1960). Comment: Mowrer on sin. *American Psychologist*, 15, 714-715
- 40 Tatelbaun, J. (1980). *The courage to grieve: Creative living, recovery and growth through grief*. New York: Harper & Row.
- 41 Tournier, P. (1966). *The person reborn*. New York: Harper & Row.
- 42 Wiener, D. N. (1961). Connotations of "Sin." *American Psychologist*, 16, 259-260.
- 43 Worden, W. J. (1982). *Grief counselling and grief therapy: A handbook for the mental health practitioner*. New York: Springer.